

Regio and Stereochemical Probes of Iodine Interactions in Diiodocyclododecanes

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Standard Coordinates [B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2-TZVP]

1,4-clcl; Gibbs Energy = -1066.124241 Hartree
Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.862395	-0.103308	1.371374
2	6	0	-0.219080	-0.575957	0.388787
3	1	0	0.974186	-0.844988	2.164118
4	1	0	0.541833	0.818940	1.863780
5	6	0	-1.623269	-0.360114	0.940668
6	6	0	-2.095414	1.088202	0.988002
7	1	0	-1.368792	1.623288	1.607718
8	1	0	-3.041570	1.139374	1.530286
9	6	0	-2.241456	1.800322	-0.359512
10	1	0	-3.180996	1.491313	-0.819165
11	1	0	-1.459519	1.467330	-1.043694
12	6	0	-2.205746	3.329297	-0.253745
13	1	0	-2.515707	3.755300	-1.212759
14	1	0	-2.951395	3.654477	0.478629
15	6	0	-0.838093	3.905025	0.129782
16	1	0	-0.944124	4.970295	0.353219
17	1	0	-0.508276	3.444371	1.063646
18	6	0	0.238319	3.728762	-0.946896
19	1	0	0.122931	2.757218	-1.431549
20	1	0	0.074524	4.468434	-1.735305
21	6	0	1.673020	3.858426	-0.423484
22	1	0	2.364524	3.903957	-1.270291
23	1	0	1.776391	4.809570	0.107827
24	6	0	2.100745	2.720296	0.510804
25	1	0	3.047440	2.979731	0.991725
26	1	0	1.373047	2.633253	1.319176
27	6	0	2.267191	1.369761	-0.204297
28	1	0	1.491930	1.237050	-0.958872
29	1	0	3.215024	1.372344	-0.742773
30	6	0	2.229226	0.194797	0.764412
31	1	0	2.955332	0.341757	1.560909
32	1	0	-1.710479	-0.809178	1.927716
33	1	0	-0.122284	-0.063028	-0.567327
34	1	0	-0.061114	-1.631895	0.180633
35	53	0	-3.050931	-1.585756	-0.210610
36	53	0	3.032819	-1.607677	-0.219635

1,4-clc2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.123711 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.693187	-0.756317	-0.335092
2	6	0	0.693193	-0.756354	0.335020
3	1	0	-0.808101	-1.687113	-0.890917
4	1	0	-0.773549	0.049645	-1.063706
5	6	0	1.816025	-0.624084	-0.686922
6	6	0	1.950998	0.750014	-1.330015
7	1	0	0.984629	0.960050	-1.798567
8	1	0	2.669796	0.692294	-2.149031
9	6	0	2.330427	1.903463	-0.392473
10	1	0	3.417438	1.956404	-0.321880
11	1	0	1.986370	1.690411	0.620451
12	6	0	1.781397	3.263709	-0.836988
13	1	0	2.256661	4.047401	-0.239275
14	1	0	2.079972	3.448596	-1.873721
15	6	0	0.259430	3.401102	-0.719890
16	1	0	-0.056207	4.328186	-1.207293
17	1	0	-0.217601	2.597632	-1.285825
18	6	0	-0.259462	3.401120	0.719881
19	1	0	0.217587	2.597678	1.285840
20	1	0	0.056161	4.328226	1.207251
21	6	0	-1.781425	3.263707	0.836998
22	1	0	-2.079986	3.448597	1.873734
23	1	0	-2.256708	4.047390	0.239288
24	6	0	-2.330452	1.903454	0.392498
25	1	0	-3.417468	1.956381	0.321959
26	1	0	-1.986443	1.690418	-0.620445
27	6	0	-1.950964	0.749997	1.330006
28	1	0	-0.984576	0.960040	1.798518
29	1	0	-2.669723	0.692252	2.149054
30	6	0	-1.815998	-0.624086	0.686881
31	1	0	1.713764	-1.386791	-1.455499
32	1	0	0.773564	0.049556	1.063691
33	1	0	0.808081	-1.687190	0.890785
34	53	0	3.724390	-1.213652	0.251444
35	53	0	-3.724387	-1.213662	-0.251431
36	1	0	-1.713704	-1.386809	1.455438

1,4-e1e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.092365 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-1.048333	0.501488	2.220262
2	6	0	-2.048993	0.975927	1.136840
3	1	0	-1.642738	0.420539	3.132745
4	1	0	-0.355019	1.320079	2.405677
5	6	0	-1.867353	2.415055	0.640009
6	6	0	-0.499642	2.912434	0.162710
7	1	0	0.206358	2.879108	0.995065
8	1	0	-0.618032	3.978334	-0.058690
9	6	0	0.101649	2.235636	-1.068529
10	1	0	-0.622564	2.287424	-1.885771
11	1	0	0.254141	1.170138	-0.889358
12	6	0	1.415526	2.882044	-1.527515
13	1	0	1.669569	2.495345	-2.518924
14	1	0	1.249331	3.957257	-1.653931
15	6	0	2.622538	2.667348	-0.602667
16	1	0	3.422048	3.338141	-0.925049
17	1	0	2.369324	2.992249	0.410117
18	6	0	3.153956	1.215730	-0.579823
19	1	0	2.523198	0.587939	-1.208759
20	1	0	4.147931	1.182849	-1.031688
21	6	0	3.236795	0.589883	0.818622
22	6	0	1.869410	0.484339	1.510455
23	6	0	1.158512	-0.856167	1.528712
24	6	0	-0.258797	-0.824863	2.146234
25	1	0	-3.043983	0.929652	1.565985
26	1	0	-0.881085	-1.600911	1.704291
27	1	0	-0.110299	-1.127388	3.187469
28	1	0	1.751677	-1.571773	2.090234
29	1	0	1.969998	0.762713	2.567189
30	1	0	1.209045	1.224820	1.077840
31	1	0	3.704908	-0.394985	0.754357
32	1	0	-2.614575	2.604621	-0.132611
33	1	0	-2.153355	3.046030	1.492002
34	1	0	3.897503	1.204663	1.435758
35	53	0	-2.414982	-0.410778	-0.535827
36	53	0	1.219794	-1.907712	-0.423151

1,4-ele2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.115694 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.807391	-0.063916	1.834500
2	6	0	-1.802068	-1.086274	1.306362
3	1	0	-1.041834	0.038956	2.900607
4	1	0	-1.039294	0.900759	1.395503
5	6	0	-3.251307	-0.578747	1.313098
6	6	0	-3.501246	0.876935	0.891654
7	1	0	-2.954887	1.539452	1.565857
8	1	0	-4.556815	1.093984	1.077696
9	6	0	-3.171695	1.233574	-0.564129
10	1	0	-3.991759	0.899106	-1.204555
11	1	0	-2.302623	0.673102	-0.900408
12	6	0	-2.910602	2.728378	-0.790254
13	1	0	-2.994338	2.949230	-1.858646
14	1	0	-3.692116	3.313976	-0.295471
15	6	0	-1.533590	3.197280	-0.298573
16	1	0	-1.500564	4.290706	-0.300493
17	1	0	-1.409411	2.906350	0.747763
18	6	0	-0.366412	2.667246	-1.139350
19	1	0	-0.523593	1.610161	-1.364909
20	1	0	-0.380019	3.173546	-2.108661
21	6	0	1.020591	2.847032	-0.508144
22	6	0	1.260525	2.003241	0.747767
23	6	0	1.240622	0.494066	0.500054
24	6	0	0.700402	-0.331624	1.662902
25	1	0	-1.742015	-2.003483	1.885312
26	1	0	0.881774	-1.391729	1.491201
27	1	0	1.235533	-0.060358	2.574682
28	1	0	2.203970	2.288903	1.213906
29	1	0	0.490402	2.236354	1.487519
30	1	0	1.786282	2.599800	-1.248605
31	1	0	-3.872990	-1.256197	0.726332
32	1	0	-3.592796	-0.680935	2.350717
33	1	0	1.168248	3.900848	-0.253877
34	53	0	-1.243428	-1.926050	-0.674991
35	53	0	3.241161	-0.209737	-0.065013
36	1	0	0.681994	0.251044	-0.396559

1,4-e2e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.122575 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.932085	-0.016360	1.544234
2	6	0	-1.774246	0.236729	0.300686
3	1	0	-1.543910	-0.509427	2.301723
4	1	0	-0.664328	0.956007	1.964889
5	6	0	-2.778452	1.376071	0.433639
6	6	0	-2.099461	2.754751	0.476412
7	1	0	-1.354951	2.767970	1.273984
8	1	0	-2.847196	3.499109	0.762536
9	6	0	-1.457118	3.175007	-0.850876
10	1	0	-2.244267	3.503384	-1.534789
11	1	0	-0.996376	2.310769	-1.333783
12	6	0	-0.407156	4.283803	-0.714124
13	1	0	-0.136561	4.643148	-1.711720
14	1	0	-0.854299	5.136370	-0.193317
15	6	0	0.865543	3.854932	0.025901
16	1	0	1.473507	4.738776	0.237878
17	1	0	0.589638	3.452829	1.003333
18	6	0	1.725589	2.836514	-0.731328
19	1	0	1.085975	2.122811	-1.255873
20	1	0	2.281066	3.355865	-1.516639
21	6	0	2.709368	2.068944	0.159079
22	6	0	2.038804	1.075665	1.112134
23	6	0	1.359248	-0.109452	0.439445
24	6	0	0.342159	-0.839507	1.309640
25	1	0	0.068819	-1.787498	0.846724
26	1	0	0.799761	-1.078433	2.272151
27	1	0	2.762072	0.706135	1.841396
28	1	0	1.276222	1.602475	1.693076
29	1	0	3.427588	1.531887	-0.464785
30	1	0	-3.473626	1.348509	-0.406972
31	1	0	-3.373084	1.223923	1.337725
32	1	0	3.289324	2.782635	0.751414
33	53	0	2.880158	-1.539348	-0.255719
34	1	0	0.908757	0.182273	-0.504118
35	1	0	-1.147846	0.393646	-0.571159
36	53	0	-2.821280	-1.612836	-0.269239

1,5-cl1e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.113361 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.078688	-0.914898	2.262251
2	6	0	-0.812296	-0.945889	1.005528
3	1	0	-0.404265	-1.507622	3.043192
4	1	0	0.129982	0.097903	2.663509
5	6	0	-1.905465	0.116577	1.053896
6	6	0	-1.445980	1.545609	0.771239
7	1	0	-0.713319	1.792674	1.547503
8	1	0	-2.284931	2.226000	0.932675
9	6	0	-0.845155	1.804032	-0.611832
10	1	0	-1.638525	1.702643	-1.353923
11	1	0	-0.114911	1.030475	-0.854977
12	6	0	-0.193969	3.184544	-0.766330
13	1	0	-0.031910	3.371473	-1.832113
14	1	0	-0.897378	3.952121	-0.427732
15	6	0	1.141653	3.362029	-0.032290
16	1	0	1.436365	4.412670	-0.087919
17	1	0	0.992979	3.164146	1.032293
18	6	0	2.282638	2.480055	-0.582668
19	1	0	1.870207	1.699230	-1.222134
20	1	0	2.930105	3.079014	-1.227179
21	6	0	3.134421	1.811518	0.504042
22	1	0	3.965044	1.273120	0.042294
23	1	0	3.581341	2.587017	1.131396
24	6	0	2.308686	0.861966	1.387197
25	1	0	2.535699	1.043399	2.445337
26	1	0	1.259563	1.113056	1.272593
27	6	0	2.467263	-0.636704	1.211552
28	1	0	3.488828	-0.940397	1.423285
29	6	0	1.506468	-1.451773	2.088420
30	1	0	-0.222030	-0.805489	0.104723
31	1	0	-1.256362	-1.936652	0.917226
32	1	0	1.484724	-2.487136	1.746411
33	53	0	-3.531556	-0.439064	-0.333800
34	53	0	2.362703	-1.273735	-0.914012
35	1	0	-2.429021	0.081077	2.007063
36	1	0	1.965281	-1.472735	3.084472

1,5cle2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.124531 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.055029	-0.659385	1.906335
2	6	0	-1.086158	-0.933536	0.799291
3	1	0	-0.350740	-1.199205	2.809147
4	1	0	-0.055595	0.396751	2.177104
5	6	0	-2.368517	-0.129876	0.974807
6	6	0	-2.233668	1.377537	0.794995
7	1	0	-1.528311	1.713576	1.561379
8	1	0	-3.185014	1.852324	1.042199
9	6	0	-1.764450	1.864126	-0.578969
10	1	0	-2.611009	1.846473	-1.266469
11	1	0	-1.035316	1.166975	-0.995258
12	6	0	-1.154311	3.270535	-0.545952
13	1	0	-1.081299	3.652254	-1.568596
14	1	0	-1.837226	3.943283	-0.017917
15	6	0	0.230435	3.330800	0.109048
16	1	0	0.491569	4.371866	0.318009
17	1	0	0.182123	2.842016	1.084985
18	6	0	1.343486	2.702212	-0.736929
19	1	0	0.965732	1.812556	-1.246229
20	1	0	1.613296	3.396786	-1.536886
21	6	0	2.606127	2.335101	0.050063
22	1	0	3.394188	2.041466	-0.647409
23	1	0	2.974093	3.221251	0.575623
24	6	0	2.407432	1.215765	1.075690
25	1	0	3.317092	1.084476	1.664833
26	1	0	1.635255	1.518768	1.788621
27	6	0	1.985795	-0.128585	0.499144
28	6	0	1.369778	-1.084383	1.514530
29	1	0	-0.660736	-0.717695	-0.180904
30	1	0	-1.320125	-1.998365	0.795253
31	1	0	1.338770	-2.095253	1.105756
32	53	0	-3.904335	-0.919074	-0.399268
33	1	0	-2.818205	-0.345334	1.941723
34	1	0	2.006311	-1.122792	2.401593
35	1	0	1.315744	0.000947	-0.344181
36	53	0	3.707427	-1.087435	-0.480632

1,5-c2e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.114957 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.653940	-1.333408	1.022948
2	6	0	-0.844470	-1.038130	-0.471050
3	1	0	-1.411008	-2.054375	1.334474
4	1	0	-0.862459	-0.438324	1.608947
5	6	0	-1.817870	0.080195	-0.818790
6	6	0	-1.385001	1.488602	-0.424675
7	1	0	-1.155182	1.518228	0.641515
8	1	0	-2.219104	2.176557	-0.569922
9	6	0	-0.192939	1.980533	-1.258978
10	1	0	-0.517073	2.063901	-2.300264
11	1	0	0.606107	1.237614	-1.256301
12	6	0	0.374133	3.331680	-0.803617
13	1	0	1.024155	3.718797	-1.594173
14	1	0	-0.446104	4.049493	-0.704005
15	6	0	1.172012	3.285811	0.506009
16	1	0	1.397784	4.309217	0.814338
17	1	0	0.535327	2.883288	1.297582
18	6	0	2.483387	2.476220	0.412980
19	1	0	2.487283	1.882927	-0.501790
20	1	0	3.330364	3.160463	0.324730
21	6	0	2.723203	1.534105	1.599744
22	1	0	3.701825	1.059019	1.500272
23	1	0	2.761083	2.125755	2.517978
24	6	0	1.624868	0.467189	1.734503
25	1	0	1.307019	0.389924	2.781848
26	1	0	0.745970	0.803676	1.195083
27	6	0	1.928813	-0.960678	1.322998
28	6	0	0.715510	-1.893773	1.429480
29	1	0	0.107904	-0.754312	-0.920643
30	1	0	-1.148599	-1.951344	-0.985200
31	1	0	0.920840	-2.824859	0.899550
32	1	0	0.648534	-2.161651	2.490939
33	53	0	-3.812515	-0.341080	0.039423
34	1	0	-2.040621	0.049671	-1.882843
35	1	0	2.745578	-1.363899	1.915426
36	53	0	2.882593	-1.100238	-0.683137

1,5-c2e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.124877 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.571713	-1.121886	-0.592626
2	6	0	1.123419	-0.850874	0.811360
3	1	0	1.150287	-1.923048	-1.053613
4	1	0	0.718635	-0.250663	-1.231451
5	6	0	2.334206	0.070019	0.895409
6	6	0	2.122921	1.488805	0.383276
7	1	0	1.773024	1.450003	-0.648367
8	1	0	3.080308	2.010439	0.356102
9	6	0	1.145009	2.299241	1.247798
10	1	0	1.643501	2.572454	2.181444
11	1	0	0.291110	1.683736	1.535688
12	6	0	0.632345	3.562518	0.544828
13	1	0	0.161119	4.218119	1.283236
14	1	0	1.485235	4.117136	0.142322
15	6	0	-0.368820	3.271958	-0.578992
16	1	0	-0.495577	4.165718	-1.195457
17	1	0	0.056741	2.518137	-1.244927
18	6	0	-1.745076	2.814364	-0.079177
19	1	0	-1.632937	2.219145	0.830100
20	1	0	-2.321129	3.692413	0.224226
21	6	0	-2.556930	2.016503	-1.104541
22	1	0	-3.572480	1.873959	-0.728366
23	1	0	-2.648153	2.599844	-2.025594
24	6	0	-1.961861	0.650842	-1.459377
25	1	0	-2.549226	0.185787	-2.253770
26	1	0	-0.960942	0.794877	-1.876857
27	6	0	-1.824157	-0.328532	-0.303485
28	6	0	-0.913456	-1.517135	-0.590032
29	1	0	0.347563	-0.388966	1.429650
30	1	0	1.359189	-1.799031	1.297335
31	1	0	-1.071787	-2.296144	0.157235
32	1	0	-1.185883	-1.949624	-1.555401
33	1	0	-1.504855	0.178210	0.601288
34	53	0	-3.815844	-1.047480	0.303841
35	53	0	4.038689	-0.837354	-0.175305
36	1	0	2.709583	0.088750	1.916161

1,5-e1e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.107457 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.721799	-1.854292	-0.767176
2	6	0	1.910969	-0.968861	-1.200585
3	1	0	0.986337	-2.886284	-1.007364
4	1	0	-0.119415	-1.595766	-1.413696
5	6	0	1.591114	0.163378	-2.180247
6	6	0	0.475351	1.165756	-1.869250
7	1	0	-0.401666	0.623754	-1.514670
8	1	0	0.167148	1.609492	-2.821435
9	6	0	0.821993	2.311321	-0.915203
10	1	0	1.662934	2.873184	-1.332585
11	1	0	1.184248	1.923772	0.037044
12	6	0	-0.350584	3.273073	-0.678099
13	1	0	0.000217	4.119330	-0.078523
14	1	0	-0.662687	3.689626	-1.641209
15	6	0	-1.570051	2.637887	0.001197
16	1	0	-2.416692	3.326217	-0.062298
17	1	0	-1.873481	1.761187	-0.566465
18	6	0	-1.338285	2.265021	1.474662
19	1	0	-0.275411	2.092459	1.649564
20	1	0	-1.593572	3.123176	2.101931
21	6	0	-2.124567	1.058161	2.003226
22	6	0	-1.748354	-0.323437	1.452083
23	6	0	-0.263102	-0.494346	1.207616
24	6	0	0.233695	-1.849674	0.687198
25	1	0	1.045877	-2.202262	1.322990
26	1	0	-0.562791	-2.593413	0.764849
27	1	0	-2.117505	-1.092961	2.124878
28	1	0	-1.940701	0.995609	3.082899
29	1	0	2.514958	0.694166	-2.420153
30	1	0	1.301993	-0.363655	-3.098844
31	1	0	-3.197680	1.219676	1.891609
32	1	0	0.211750	-0.284441	2.172911
33	1	0	2.647120	-1.598638	-1.689062
34	53	0	3.201698	-0.276826	0.470779
35	1	0	0.081916	0.294129	0.551596
36	53	0	-2.952694	-0.855858	-0.345241

1,5-e1e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.114838 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.667263	-0.496058	1.530240
2	6	0	-2.173485	-0.650941	1.385459
3	1	0	-0.493164	-0.490791	2.612985
4	1	0	-0.391824	0.498256	1.192382
5	6	0	-2.959529	0.574515	1.873124
6	6	0	-2.403313	1.964868	1.530903
7	1	0	-1.407458	2.064451	1.966858
8	1	0	-3.016826	2.700785	2.058165
9	6	0	-2.356576	2.335021	0.042396
10	1	0	-3.355551	2.641671	-0.277766
11	1	0	-2.124864	1.456494	-0.555142
12	6	0	-1.343110	3.437929	-0.289605
13	1	0	-1.578220	3.857088	-1.272668
14	1	0	-1.449624	4.259573	0.425740
15	6	0	0.114877	2.956747	-0.296802
16	1	0	0.783449	3.821283	-0.337683
17	1	0	0.332851	2.467138	0.655590
18	6	0	0.444860	2.021136	-1.465843
19	1	0	-0.359306	1.296308	-1.601335
20	1	0	0.467449	2.609442	-2.387387
21	6	0	1.786550	1.276981	-1.342010
22	6	0	1.782099	0.246355	-0.219572
23	6	0	0.864185	-0.954616	-0.441215
24	6	0	0.268258	-1.512201	0.855319
25	1	0	-0.263779	-2.440995	0.644406
26	1	0	1.083288	-1.767827	1.536097
27	1	0	2.014626	0.777073	-2.286452
28	1	0	-3.997428	0.490223	1.548408
29	1	0	-2.979660	0.492452	2.966990
30	1	0	2.584647	2.001225	-1.168921
31	1	0	1.392153	-1.736243	-0.987679
32	1	0	-2.514645	-1.530951	1.923187
33	53	0	-2.826511	-1.264862	-0.652998
34	1	0	0.044713	-0.639272	-1.088986
35	53	0	3.836330	-0.447586	0.176287
36	1	0	1.563457	0.733901	0.724492

1,5-e2e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.126083 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.823308	-0.739832	0.988005
2	6	0	-1.908339	0.126768	0.363809
3	1	0	-1.272077	-1.394988	1.736711
4	1	0	-0.155466	-0.075412	1.544759
5	6	0	-2.420682	1.248057	1.260690
6	6	0	-1.407020	2.398515	1.375119
7	1	0	-0.432830	1.994870	1.655616
8	1	0	-1.704475	3.047603	2.202796
9	6	0	-1.285882	3.236708	0.096877
10	1	0	-2.148343	3.905437	0.032183
11	1	0	-1.357759	2.589209	-0.779619
12	6	0	0.000305	4.065576	0.000111
13	1	0	-0.068542	4.723057	-0.872128
14	1	0	0.069278	4.722851	0.872495
15	6	0	1.286332	3.236491	-0.096880
16	1	0	2.148930	3.905045	-0.032189
17	1	0	1.358177	2.588856	0.779520
18	6	0	1.407158	2.398427	-1.375229
19	1	0	0.432849	1.995018	-1.655648
20	1	0	1.704655	3.047535	-2.202876
21	6	0	2.420588	1.247743	-1.260995
22	6	0	1.908263	0.126666	-0.363841
23	6	0	0.823104	-0.740007	-0.987717
24	6	0	-0.000053	-1.569983	0.000262
25	1	0	-0.669909	-2.223353	-0.562649
26	1	0	0.669845	-2.223178	0.563328
27	1	0	2.643124	0.839638	-2.249792
28	1	0	-3.358105	1.640987	0.864379
29	1	0	-2.643542	0.840081	2.249467
30	1	0	3.358187	1.640517	-0.864946
31	1	0	1.271760	-1.395313	-1.736359
32	1	0	0.155199	-0.075683	-1.544509
33	53	0	3.587618	-1.145031	0.279375
34	1	0	1.584714	0.532443	0.588983
35	1	0	-1.584602	0.532339	-0.589039
36	53	0	-3.587691	-1.144937	-0.279408

1,6-cl1e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.114509 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.008997	-2.010956	0.435516
2	6	0	1.364470	-1.332449	0.739607
3	1	0	0.175959	-3.071055	0.233421
4	1	0	-0.427779	-1.599879	-0.474532
5	6	0	1.968463	-0.658246	-0.487226
6	6	0	1.235984	0.575742	-1.003922
7	1	0	0.217100	0.247660	-1.231771
8	1	0	1.673486	0.869181	-1.960514
9	6	0	1.186443	1.800019	-0.086532
10	1	0	2.181516	2.245378	-0.043295
11	1	0	0.957438	1.499417	0.938234
12	6	0	0.176310	2.858303	-0.552288
13	1	0	0.348193	3.784549	0.004814
14	1	0	0.377385	3.093744	-1.601838
15	6	0	-1.290880	2.438153	-0.402999
16	1	0	-1.923497	3.079046	-1.022306
17	1	0	-1.413518	1.438294	-0.813517
18	6	0	-1.800986	2.483397	1.044010
19	1	0	-0.984528	2.247706	1.729188
20	1	0	-2.086232	3.510865	1.286168
21	6	0	-2.999264	1.581778	1.373145
22	1	0	-3.271874	1.769353	2.419073
23	1	0	-3.868671	1.870960	0.781431
24	6	0	-2.790720	0.064400	1.269089
25	1	0	-3.581984	-0.446270	1.810800
26	6	0	-1.428831	-0.389094	1.764855
27	6	0	-1.012202	-1.855414	1.568916
28	1	0	1.256334	-0.593082	1.533851
29	1	0	2.060983	-2.077669	1.122151
30	1	0	-0.575633	-2.236378	2.495482
31	1	0	-1.886861	-2.475263	1.362100
32	1	0	-1.425115	-0.137666	2.832628
33	53	0	4.086772	-0.175183	-0.082964
34	1	0	2.072025	-1.380741	-1.293764
35	1	0	-0.670025	0.245690	1.319455
36	53	0	-3.273780	-0.677980	-0.773645

1,6-c1e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.125039 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.092379	-1.626972	-0.549536
2	6	0	1.410309	-1.253513	0.147529
3	1	0	0.270373	-2.486799	-1.199974
4	1	0	-0.229986	-0.820697	-1.211098
5	6	0	2.381032	-0.530397	-0.777531
6	6	0	1.978067	0.884747	-1.174989
7	1	0	1.008448	0.793206	-1.674096
8	1	0	2.668453	1.253320	-1.935945
9	6	0	1.876400	1.908842	-0.040442
10	1	0	2.877402	2.271081	0.196703
11	1	0	1.519979	1.423778	0.869632
12	6	0	0.967319	3.098865	-0.369686
13	1	0	1.122347	3.881247	0.379342
14	1	0	1.274874	3.529625	-1.327537
15	6	0	-0.524721	2.752815	-0.428148
16	1	0	-1.076848	3.592000	-0.859765
17	1	0	-0.668540	1.922897	-1.123654
18	6	0	-1.133950	2.408220	0.935319
19	1	0	-0.426505	1.821203	1.523057
20	1	0	-1.286956	3.332101	1.499483
21	6	0	-2.476200	1.662655	0.856744
22	1	0	-2.920612	1.594984	1.852686
23	1	0	-3.169181	2.240651	0.242909
24	6	0	-2.334066	0.260286	0.276996
25	6	0	-1.593381	-0.730958	1.164142
26	6	0	-1.038409	-1.955716	0.432398
27	1	0	1.217237	-0.630219	1.021000
28	1	0	1.873817	-2.165155	0.525451
29	1	0	-0.674405	-2.674380	1.171850
30	1	0	-1.852644	-2.449834	-0.102594
31	1	0	-2.245957	-1.043143	1.981254
32	53	0	4.388586	-0.513672	0.141909
33	1	0	2.563563	-1.125550	-1.669574
34	1	0	-0.765634	-0.193516	1.634970
35	53	0	-4.328595	-0.536289	-0.215879
36	1	0	-1.887425	0.307900	-0.710421

1,6-c2e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.114767 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.635944	-0.916860	1.518909
2	6	0	1.488079	0.337402	1.789154
3	1	0	1.217833	-1.807116	1.759815
4	1	0	0.410858	-0.993772	0.455884
5	6	0	2.149238	0.975114	0.572315
6	6	0	1.203724	1.504134	-0.499846
7	1	0	0.497948	0.719646	-0.773456
8	1	0	1.770718	1.728821	-1.404069
9	6	0	0.457553	2.778259	-0.073580
10	1	0	1.179427	3.596114	0.004419
11	1	0	0.035861	2.661876	0.927101
12	6	0	-0.654946	3.177168	-1.054632
13	1	0	-0.999285	4.187644	-0.812407
14	1	0	-0.228145	3.232771	-2.060408
15	6	0	-1.851170	2.217869	-1.068151
16	1	0	-2.440870	2.380549	-1.973681
17	1	0	-1.482523	1.198080	-1.149868
18	6	0	-2.768742	2.355084	0.155460
19	1	0	-2.182185	2.662938	1.023137
20	1	0	-3.469345	3.176430	-0.018429
21	6	0	-3.593962	1.116166	0.531593
22	1	0	-4.237420	1.396730	1.374601
23	1	0	-4.268230	0.845862	-0.282006
24	6	0	-2.826616	-0.129938	0.997046
25	6	0	-1.629129	0.196414	1.871783
26	6	0	-0.684066	-0.938096	2.299096
27	1	0	0.867268	1.119082	2.239338
28	1	0	2.255629	0.112920	2.530932
29	1	0	-0.469368	-0.847102	3.367082
30	1	0	-1.170034	-1.906584	2.165383
31	1	0	-2.056776	0.682309	2.757689
32	1	0	-1.043306	0.964915	1.378691
33	1	0	2.835002	1.757350	0.890652
34	53	0	3.544037	-0.472061	-0.344388
35	53	0	-2.318963	-1.454517	-0.715115
36	1	0	-3.507424	-0.797168	1.518373

1,6-c2e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.124950 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.584841	-1.107261	0.762890
2	6	0	1.581744	-0.222939	1.518735
3	1	0	1.051640	-2.071956	0.562227
4	1	0	0.372945	-0.680957	-0.219360
5	6	0	2.630218	0.496125	0.678278
6	6	0	2.087704	1.517473	-0.313438
7	1	0	1.333286	1.041817	-0.940220
8	1	0	2.884394	1.832892	-0.987790
9	6	0	1.508050	2.760395	0.379583
10	1	0	2.334905	3.376577	0.742224
11	1	0	0.943993	2.469987	1.267367
12	6	0	0.606111	3.600537	-0.532924
13	1	0	0.417681	4.567023	-0.055493
14	1	0	1.140742	3.817123	-1.462514
15	6	0	-0.734278	2.934116	-0.861882
16	1	0	-1.227270	3.486319	-1.666026
17	1	0	-0.543482	1.939012	-1.268693
18	6	0	-1.688922	2.840273	0.335067
19	1	0	-1.123792	2.668697	1.252513
20	1	0	-2.183060	3.805499	0.473337
21	6	0	-2.771827	1.758746	0.194174
22	1	0	-3.505466	1.863347	0.997173
23	1	0	-3.309328	1.913955	-0.742879
24	6	0	-2.201430	0.344947	0.222236
25	6	0	-1.637994	-0.093726	1.566122
26	6	0	-0.729859	-1.325475	1.519685
27	1	0	1.040079	0.559298	2.059895
28	1	0	2.083109	-0.817941	2.284313
29	1	0	-0.507694	-1.635347	2.544986
30	1	0	-1.277358	-2.152121	1.062117
31	1	0	-2.461122	-0.259006	2.264072
32	1	0	-1.071148	0.750229	1.970463
33	53	0	-3.756297	-1.074473	-0.427858
34	1	0	-1.467521	0.219090	-0.566864
35	1	0	3.367849	0.960436	1.329164
36	53	0	3.875173	-0.975966	-0.396881

1,6-e1e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.104373 Hartree
Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-1.703113	0.964666	-1.912112
2	6	0	-2.302134	-0.380385	-1.444911
3	1	0	-2.252537	1.247415	-2.812793
4	1	0	-0.679846	0.767084	-2.237526
5	6	0	-1.344542	-1.572652	-1.455153
6	6	0	0.015439	-1.464857	-0.762639
7	1	0	0.544017	-0.588193	-1.130156
8	1	0	0.615027	-2.316719	-1.096570
9	6	0	-0.015634	-1.464102	0.762660
10	1	0	-0.615793	-2.315242	1.097392
11	1	0	-0.543666	-0.586739	1.129278
12	6	0	1.344230	-1.572052	1.455352
13	1	0	1.146588	-1.750921	2.520446
14	1	0	1.875204	-2.456864	1.097717
15	6	0	2.302070	-0.379991	1.445022
16	6	0	1.703311	0.965294	1.911923
17	6	0	1.699670	2.196534	0.995905
18	6	0	0.737967	2.174936	-0.193334
19	6	0	-0.738078	2.175485	0.192673
20	6	0	-1.699719	2.196326	-0.996645
21	1	0	-2.714908	2.366470	-0.633910
22	1	0	-1.451344	3.057537	-1.625302
23	1	0	1.451267	3.058020	1.624173
24	1	0	-1.875655	-2.457279	-1.097244
25	1	0	-1.147054	-1.751789	-2.520242
26	1	0	2.714817	2.366598	0.633019
27	1	0	-0.941301	3.059449	0.806220
28	1	0	-0.968030	1.321272	0.827888
29	1	0	0.941585	3.058124	-0.807865
30	1	0	0.967492	1.319928	-0.827617
31	1	0	0.680138	0.767866	2.237786
32	1	0	2.253096	1.248394	2.812280
33	53	0	-3.480185	-0.294039	0.439626
34	1	0	-3.128174	-0.637237	-2.099255
35	1	0	3.127973	-0.636904	2.099518
36	53	0	3.480267	-0.294177	-0.439432

1,6-ele2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.115346 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	1.526802	0.574139	1.731384
2	6	0	2.548418	-0.469848	1.315459
3	1	0	1.386909	0.410282	2.807083
4	1	0	0.573221	0.323638	1.278344
5	6	0	2.044882	-1.910878	1.480365
6	6	0	0.579439	-2.193692	1.120071
7	1	0	-0.063295	-1.584587	1.758537
8	1	0	0.363052	-3.226615	1.405448
9	6	0	0.189617	-1.994085	-0.351123
10	1	0	0.477389	-2.880389	-0.921578
11	1	0	0.760014	-1.178466	-0.787640
12	6	0	-1.311376	-1.733201	-0.559315
13	1	0	-1.577320	-1.908408	-1.604303
14	1	0	-1.887756	-2.445463	0.033555
15	6	0	-1.713101	-0.307264	-0.187645
16	1	0	-1.421445	-0.082148	0.833581
17	6	0	-1.216585	0.755746	-1.157823
18	6	0	-1.360996	2.213707	-0.709416
19	6	0	-0.523529	2.595964	0.516586
20	6	0	0.998222	2.587967	0.271274
21	6	0	1.814672	2.059043	1.457209
22	1	0	2.880079	2.210183	1.271719
23	1	0	1.570244	2.644739	2.347081
24	1	0	-1.074728	2.854545	-1.548603
25	1	0	2.707359	-2.591634	0.944472
26	1	0	2.168736	-2.146452	2.544483
27	1	0	-2.414430	2.421852	-0.509455
28	1	0	1.331808	3.598005	0.021781
29	1	0	1.232004	1.977199	-0.601441
30	1	0	-0.829493	3.588572	0.855211
31	1	0	-0.776694	1.926520	1.342636
32	1	0	-0.159240	0.547060	-1.346441
33	53	0	-3.909634	-0.199028	-0.019381
34	1	0	-1.721487	0.615846	-2.116230
35	53	0	3.372780	-0.136728	-0.724924
36	1	0	3.469528	-0.344774	1.877747

1,6-e2e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.125958 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-1.846529	0.763359	-1.291252
2	6	0	-2.199212	-0.310577	-0.272014
3	1	0	-2.537434	0.699716	-2.134080
4	1	0	-0.861312	0.515265	-1.696502
5	6	0	-1.837297	-1.732598	-0.686853
6	6	0	-0.319641	-1.975348	-0.696955
7	1	0	0.160927	-1.230396	-1.333016
8	1	0	-0.125179	-2.937365	-1.177652
9	6	0	0.319672	-1.975379	0.697347
10	1	0	0.125253	-2.937424	1.178007
11	1	0	-0.160925	-1.230489	1.333437
12	6	0	1.837311	-1.732538	0.687220
13	1	0	2.251212	-1.931637	1.678538
14	1	0	2.305620	-2.442892	0.003839
15	6	0	2.199180	-0.310538	0.272260
16	1	0	1.770169	-0.081880	-0.697668
17	6	0	1.846833	0.763487	1.291534
18	6	0	1.812445	2.193546	0.744765
19	6	0	0.709573	2.439255	-0.290743
20	6	0	-0.709251	2.439333	0.290863
21	6	0	-1.812114	2.193485	-0.744632
22	1	0	-2.784639	2.428620	-0.306179
23	1	0	-1.677544	2.882827	-1.583206
24	1	0	1.677961	2.883005	1.583258
25	1	0	-2.305631	-2.442958	-0.003482
26	1	0	-2.251125	-1.931710	-1.678202
27	1	0	2.784960	2.428553	0.306223
28	1	0	-0.887486	3.398295	0.784263
29	1	0	-0.788336	1.691001	1.083214
30	1	0	0.887841	3.398129	-0.784301
31	1	0	0.788626	1.690781	-1.082971
32	1	0	-1.770388	-0.081925	0.697994
33	1	0	0.861678	0.515539	1.697012
34	53	0	-4.349961	-0.212372	0.195038
35	53	0	4.349810	-0.212455	-0.195265
36	1	0	2.537920	0.699869	2.134226

1,7-clcl; Gibbs Energy = -1066.124261 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.850927	-1.934216	1.449207
2	6	0	-1.759334	-1.405797	0.329196
3	1	0	-1.435116	-2.596197	2.093986
4	1	0	-0.519330	-1.113153	2.087274
5	6	0	-2.778774	-0.387766	0.823229
6	6	0	-2.206466	0.935689	1.314915
7	1	0	-1.549659	0.688219	2.154574
8	1	0	-3.011793	1.538056	1.738871
9	6	0	-1.432705	1.768089	0.286151
10	1	0	-2.140493	2.366878	-0.287988
11	1	0	-0.950204	1.112532	-0.440257
12	6	0	-0.377880	2.682586	0.918768
13	1	0	-0.053374	3.422612	0.181595
14	1	0	-0.836334	3.247121	1.736409
15	6	0	0.850923	1.934132	1.449290
16	1	0	1.435117	2.596066	2.094111
17	1	0	0.519297	1.113036	2.087295
18	6	0	1.759333	1.405769	0.329246
19	1	0	1.160752	0.959324	-0.464841
20	1	0	2.280275	2.249690	-0.124701
21	6	0	2.778793	0.387714	0.823249
22	1	0	3.406103	0.826653	1.596046
23	6	0	2.206460	-0.935746	1.314868
24	6	0	1.432713	-1.768128	0.286121
25	6	0	0.377893	-2.682621	0.918691
26	1	0	-1.160760	-0.959365	-0.464901
27	1	0	-2.280282	-2.249687	-0.124796
28	1	0	0.053419	-3.422673	0.181530
29	1	0	0.836322	-3.247176	1.736335
30	1	0	2.140493	-2.366889	-0.288057
31	1	0	0.950232	-1.112578	-0.440308
32	1	0	3.011755	-1.538124	1.738867
33	1	0	-3.406101	-0.826733	1.595991
34	1	0	1.549666	-0.688284	2.154543
35	53	0	-4.258047	-0.017027	-0.773576
36	53	0	4.258045	0.017073	-0.773578

1,7-clc2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.124392 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.916286	2.167518	-0.894828
2	6	0	-2.060763	1.498875	-0.116196
3	1	0	-1.343323	2.794474	-1.681444
4	1	0	-0.314473	1.415778	-1.407661
5	6	0	-2.678436	0.322700	-0.861353
6	6	0	-1.774693	-0.889656	-1.048845
7	1	0	-0.923051	-0.544847	-1.643226
8	1	0	-2.288586	-1.625796	-1.669778
9	6	0	-1.265859	-1.567466	0.226195
10	1	0	-2.057430	-2.200959	0.628489
11	1	0	-1.070628	-0.818698	0.996073
12	6	0	0.000178	-2.401833	0.000078
13	1	0	0.155548	-3.059541	0.860469
14	1	0	-0.155245	-3.059932	-0.860008
15	6	0	1.266262	-1.567599	-0.226122
16	1	0	2.057885	-2.201096	-0.628333
17	1	0	1.071109	-0.818877	-0.996035
18	6	0	1.774780	-0.889609	1.048925
19	1	0	0.922975	-0.544774	1.643095
20	1	0	2.288632	-1.625632	1.670018
21	6	0	2.678489	0.322768	0.861410
22	6	0	2.060716	1.498896	0.116298
23	6	0	0.916069	2.167316	0.894857
24	6	0	-0.000029	3.010801	0.000053
25	1	0	-1.708556	1.159314	0.857908
26	1	0	-2.829585	2.245216	0.086423
27	1	0	-0.613680	3.666804	0.624319
28	1	0	0.613663	3.666823	-0.624169
29	1	0	1.342975	2.794066	1.681734
30	1	0	0.314187	1.415443	1.407477
31	1	0	2.829445	2.245368	-0.086219
32	1	0	-3.062338	0.646638	-1.826294
33	1	0	1.708637	1.159353	-0.857853
34	53	0	-4.540948	-0.277313	0.161858
35	53	0	4.540889	-0.277255	-0.161937
36	1	0	3.062387	0.646700	1.826351

1,7-e1e1; Gibbs Energy = -1066.103566 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	2.316945	1.739343	-1.176573
2	6	0	2.802831	1.002697	0.091964
3	1	0	3.213797	2.103021	-1.683015
4	1	0	1.780775	2.631869	-0.846685
5	6	0	2.348310	1.603232	1.423628
6	6	0	0.864824	1.887437	1.669002
7	1	0	0.480259	2.513052	0.862467
8	1	0	0.805504	2.508483	2.569206
9	6	0	-0.033827	0.670155	1.864919
10	1	0	0.384859	0.048142	2.661443
11	1	0	-0.027755	0.041259	0.979236
12	6	0	-1.474447	1.020257	2.239450
13	1	0	-1.994833	0.108877	2.538403
14	1	0	-1.457722	1.666737	3.123334
15	6	0	-2.316173	1.739438	1.176724
16	1	0	-3.212852	2.103692	1.683062
17	1	0	-1.779447	2.631620	0.846844
18	6	0	-2.802460	1.003022	-0.091792
19	1	0	-3.887033	1.014867	-0.101283
20	6	0	-2.348052	1.603656	-1.423457
21	6	0	-0.864592	1.887910	-1.669044
22	6	0	0.034188	0.670615	-1.864256
23	6	0	1.474738	1.020546	-2.239168
24	1	0	1.994873	0.109108	-2.538377
25	1	0	1.457912	1.667139	-3.122968
26	1	0	-2.745444	0.995166	-2.238382
27	1	0	2.745608	0.994676	2.238548
28	1	0	2.874882	2.565038	1.482907
29	1	0	-2.874615	2.565474	-1.482618
30	1	0	-0.384548	0.048003	-2.660279
31	1	0	0.028286	0.042338	-0.978137
32	1	0	-0.805438	2.508390	-2.569649
33	1	0	-0.480041	2.514123	-0.862950
34	53	0	-2.555598	-1.202581	-0.063132
35	53	0	2.555255	-1.202800	0.062922
36	1	0	3.887406	1.014282	0.101653

1,7-e1e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.115070 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-1.479191	0.102091	1.900933
2	6	0	-1.520750	0.603039	0.463980
3	1	0	-2.435872	0.324162	2.379772
4	1	0	-0.737029	0.709970	2.429939
5	6	0	-1.691283	2.113005	0.315747
6	6	0	-0.417913	2.907517	0.652059
7	1	0	-0.090611	2.662036	1.664321
8	1	0	-0.683118	3.966549	0.685397
9	6	0	0.732748	2.693850	-0.354693
10	1	0	0.780161	3.543629	-1.039213
11	1	0	0.521468	1.826116	-0.979721
12	6	0	2.107951	2.499371	0.296746
13	1	0	2.874021	2.430613	-0.478852
14	1	0	2.346862	3.388365	0.886220
15	6	0	2.161934	1.264124	1.209462
16	1	0	2.673937	1.517379	2.146287
17	1	0	1.150056	1.003156	1.501007
18	6	0	2.862102	0.010563	0.718714
19	1	0	3.911317	0.213559	0.522164
20	6	0	2.748913	-1.166370	1.697840
21	6	0	1.406592	-1.366216	2.415025
22	6	0	0.220752	-1.807665	1.543033
23	6	0	-1.145526	-1.382786	2.091439
24	1	0	-1.924780	-1.976127	1.609839
25	1	0	-1.200233	-1.612554	3.160171
26	1	0	3.055717	-2.087091	1.199691
27	1	0	-1.977496	2.344411	-0.711130
28	1	0	-2.517273	2.441431	0.951661
29	1	0	3.505604	-0.974939	2.468817
30	1	0	0.244141	-2.895064	1.439502
31	1	0	0.330288	-1.427762	0.529944
32	1	0	-0.658157	0.261855	-0.099899
33	53	0	-3.152256	-0.402234	-0.628113
34	1	0	1.562016	-2.112885	3.198439
35	1	0	1.151906	-0.448866	2.948832
36	53	0	2.250352	-0.577409	-1.336319

1,7-e2e2; Gibbs Energy = -1066.126265 Hartree
 Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	2.147618	0.770957	1.514402
2	6	0	2.130232	-0.299489	0.432757
3	1	0	3.130756	0.784268	1.989064
4	1	0	1.448038	0.452807	2.292847
5	6	0	2.115416	-1.730298	0.959474
6	6	0	0.750531	-2.111829	1.554923
7	1	0	0.446934	-1.353111	2.278298
8	1	0	0.865102	-3.034020	2.130329
9	6	0	-0.349211	-2.311795	0.504296
10	1	0	-0.229226	-3.299065	0.051305
11	1	0	-0.216563	-1.604173	-0.317426
12	6	0	-1.773842	-2.182563	1.053114
13	1	0	-2.484891	-2.506452	0.289867
14	1	0	-1.897369	-2.865178	1.899099
15	6	0	-2.147618	-0.770957	1.514403
16	1	0	-3.130756	-0.784268	1.989064
17	1	0	-1.448038	-0.452807	2.292847
18	6	0	-2.130232	0.299489	0.432757
19	6	0	-2.115416	1.730298	0.959474
20	6	0	-0.750531	2.111829	1.554923
21	6	0	0.349211	2.311795	0.504296
22	6	0	1.773842	2.182563	1.053114
23	1	0	2.484891	2.506452	0.289867
24	1	0	1.897369	2.865178	1.899099
25	1	0	-2.355550	2.423929	0.152274
26	1	0	2.355549	-2.423929	0.152274
27	1	0	2.899592	-1.840555	1.712312
28	1	0	-2.899592	1.840555	1.712312
29	1	0	0.229226	3.299065	0.051305
30	1	0	0.216563	1.604173	-0.317426
31	1	0	-0.865102	3.034020	2.130329
32	1	0	-0.446934	1.353111	2.278297
33	1	0	1.305626	-0.147195	-0.255736
34	1	0	-1.305626	0.147195	-0.255736
35	53	0	3.851768	-0.020175	-0.912001
36	53	0	-3.851768	0.020175	-0.912001

c; Gibbs Energy = -768.901783 Hartree

Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.922440	-1.978541	0.939388
2	6	0	-0.228024	-1.415866	0.090674
3	1	0	0.508038	-2.670454	1.677539
4	1	0	1.395928	-1.179672	1.512033
5	6	0	-1.071299	-0.396935	0.846182
6	1	0	0.160268	-0.956694	-0.818350
7	1	0	-0.859738	-2.243319	-0.234369
8	6	0	-0.382295	0.924386	1.163678
9	1	0	-1.463947	-0.836904	1.760325
10	1	0	0.489691	0.670383	1.773980
11	1	0	-1.031124	1.520382	1.808205
12	6	0	0.061716	1.768783	-0.035264
13	1	0	-0.791643	2.344991	-0.395110
14	1	0	0.345749	1.119571	-0.864661
15	6	0	1.224252	2.716153	0.284746
16	1	0	1.322635	3.444407	-0.526024
17	1	0	0.978665	3.291966	1.182728
18	6	0	2.569689	2.009047	0.485903
19	1	0	3.288300	2.710688	0.919307
20	1	0	2.448172	1.218483	1.229709
21	6	0	3.160306	1.426557	-0.801746
22	1	0	2.367502	0.966275	-1.394857
23	1	0	3.543915	2.247294	-1.414803
24	6	0	4.278712	0.401415	-0.579544
25	1	0	4.731542	0.155312	-1.545358
26	1	0	5.070700	0.861050	0.020403
27	6	0	3.824097	-0.893368	0.104559
28	1	0	4.702518	-1.495506	0.353116
29	1	0	3.362955	-0.644388	1.062398
30	6	0	2.858862	-1.745004	-0.729790
31	1	0	2.206390	-1.098221	-1.319378
32	1	0	3.433061	-2.323216	-1.458728
33	6	0	1.992356	-2.694707	0.105407
34	1	0	1.504559	-3.419538	-0.553460
35	1	0	2.637401	-3.273565	0.773640
36	53	0	-2.936159	-0.021526	-0.279122

e1; Gibbs Energy = -768.891499 Hartree

Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	-0.032937	0.515003	1.699065
2	6	0	1.229514	-0.238389	1.324016
3	1	0	-0.183899	0.290022	2.762411
4	1	0	-0.871931	0.055495	1.187952
5	6	0	1.100923	-1.758977	1.494116
6	1	0	2.075835	0.118850	1.904328
7	6	0	-0.242051	-2.401653	1.118351
8	1	0	-1.029148	-1.949683	1.724509
9	1	0	-0.205291	-3.447742	1.435153
10	6	0	-0.634623	-2.345534	-0.365096
11	1	0	-0.136859	-3.162405	-0.894024
12	1	0	-0.250881	-1.436179	-0.821411
13	6	0	-2.147482	-2.420386	-0.608552
14	1	0	-2.326524	-2.661436	-1.660990
15	1	0	-2.568258	-3.249480	-0.030066
16	6	0	-2.905416	-1.128742	-0.268065
17	1	0	-3.981360	-1.322845	-0.314558
18	1	0	-2.705821	-0.853719	0.770836
19	6	0	-2.576432	0.042487	-1.199282
20	1	0	-1.494582	0.130771	-1.317401
21	1	0	-2.960306	-0.194006	-2.196333
22	6	0	-3.143328	1.398246	-0.758135
23	1	0	-3.043020	2.106599	-1.586620
24	1	0	-4.217807	1.294647	-0.574482
25	6	0	-2.477235	2.001439	0.486008
26	1	0	-3.047213	2.879155	0.800719
27	1	0	-2.564842	1.292401	1.312588
28	6	0	-0.999647	2.397905	0.284723
29	1	0	-0.603130	1.912235	-0.607506
30	1	0	-0.930831	3.471474	0.093586
31	6	0	-0.094892	2.034283	1.469017
32	1	0	0.908024	2.434335	1.304874
33	1	0	-0.476703	2.520805	2.370397
34	1	0	1.920846	-2.255361	0.973332
35	1	0	1.265430	-1.947792	2.562299
36	53	0	1.980564	0.290562	-0.702954

e2; Gibbs Energy = -768.902509 Hartree

Standard orientation:

Center Number	Atomic Number	Atomic Type	Coordinates (Angstroms)		
			X	Y	Z
1	6	0	0.357072	0.799263	1.338904
2	6	0	0.710996	-0.289926	0.337033
3	1	0	1.126124	0.839191	2.112884
4	1	0	-0.558735	0.483257	1.846420
5	6	0	0.520752	-1.713324	0.849102
6	6	0	-0.964183	-2.093906	0.967900
7	1	0	-1.483859	-1.341413	1.562748
8	1	0	-1.040635	-3.023321	1.538503
9	6	0	-1.666211	-2.275280	-0.383400
10	1	0	-1.389750	-3.249369	-0.795969
11	1	0	-1.290863	-1.540986	-1.099005
12	6	0	-3.194376	-2.168533	-0.317753
13	1	0	-3.612552	-2.469335	-1.283498
14	1	0	-3.571291	-2.888715	0.415542
15	6	0	-3.715102	-0.771281	0.040500
16	1	0	-4.792684	-0.825853	0.219749
17	1	0	-3.277806	-0.462104	0.991999
18	6	0	-3.444979	0.297095	-1.024654
19	1	0	-2.453940	0.148358	-1.458088
20	1	0	-4.148637	0.159114	-1.850478
21	6	0	-3.547628	1.735478	-0.502470
22	1	0	-3.554244	2.427618	-1.350383
23	1	0	-4.509914	1.862851	0.003442
24	6	0	-2.417263	2.130420	0.455580
25	1	0	-2.673464	3.070376	0.952368
26	1	0	-2.354751	1.387480	1.253571
27	6	0	-1.049550	2.286687	-0.219536
28	1	0	-0.934641	1.537192	-1.005813
29	1	0	-1.016896	3.250519	-0.734592
30	6	0	0.139917	2.193043	0.742590
31	1	0	1.051338	2.503453	0.226273
32	1	0	-0.005228	2.901070	1.563972
33	1	0	1.013621	-2.415867	0.175150
34	1	0	1.012662	-1.811490	1.819941
35	53	0	2.790877	-0.022038	-0.343637
36	1	0	0.172980	-0.152434	-0.594735